

Synthesis and Reactions of N-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)-Acetohydrazonyl Chloride

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Dehydrochlorination of N-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-acetohydrazonyl chloride, prepared by chlorinating the corresponding hydrazone, with triethylamine afforded a highly reactive nitrile imine. Its 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions with various groups of dipolarophiles and also nucleophilic substitution reactions with selected nucleophiles have been investigated. These reactions ultimately result in the formation of novel heterocyclic and acyclic compounds.

THE chemistry of hydrazonyl halides has engaged the attention of chemists because of their importance as useful intermediates in the synthesis of novel heterocycles. In spite of the wide applicability of diphenyl hydrazonyl halides¹⁻⁴ in synthetic studies, no information is available concerning the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of C-alkyl derivatives of hydrazonyl halides. The present investigation has been undertaken with a view of studying systematically the cycloaddition as well as nucleophilic substitution reactions of N-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-acetohydrazonyl chloride with various groups of dipolarophiles and nucleophiles.

Results and Discussion

Treatment of acetaldehyde-2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone with dry chlorine gas in chloroform leads to the replacement of methine hydrogen giving N-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-acetohydrazonyl chloride (1) in excellent yield.

The chloride (1) when treated with triethylamine in dry benzene immediately generated a dark red colouration due to the formation of C-methyl-N-2,4-dinitrophenyl nitrile imine (2), which on subsequent reaction with various groups of dipolarophiles afforded five membered heterocyclic derivatives (4-13), or underwent spontaneous dimerization to form 1,4-dihydro-1,2,4,5-tetrazine (3), in absence of any other coreactant (Scheme 1). The formation of tetrazine is the common fate of nitrile imine⁵, and can feasibly be regarded as a 1,3-dipolar addition of initially generated nitrile imine onto a ground state hydrazonyl moiety.

Addition of nitrile imine (2) onto olefinic double bond of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds like benzylideneacetophenone and benzylidene-4-bromoacetophenone in dry benzene under reflux for 1-4 hr afforded Δ^2 -pyrazolines (4) and (5), respectively (Scheme 1).

The ability of nitrile imine to undergo cycloaddition reactions is not restricted to their attack on C-C multiple bonds, and it is found that compounds containing C-O double bond may also be used as dipolarophiles⁷. In an attempt to investigate the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of 2 with C=O bond, we have carried out its reaction with normal ketones but no cycloadduct was isolated even in traces. However, it is interesting to note that 1,3,4-oxadiazolines (6-11) are obtained in appreciable yields (Scheme 1) when the same imine (2) is allowed to add on aromatic aldehydes.

The structural assignment of these oxadiazolines are made on the basis of nmr spectra. The presence of hydroxyl protons in compounds (8-11) are also confirmed from deuterium exchange studies.

Azomethines add to the nitrile imine more readily than the carbonyl compounds⁸. This emphasizes the superiority of the Schiffs bases as dipolarophiles over carbonyl compounds. Thus, nitrile imine (2), when treated with Schiffs bases under reflux afforded 1,2,4- Δ^2 -triazolines (12) and (13), as a high melting crystalline stuff (Scheme 1). Usually, the reaction takes place in polar solvent like chloroform or methanol, and the conventional workup of the reaction mixture yields Δ^2 -triazolines exclusively.

Furthermore, the reaction of hydrazonyl chloride (1), with an equimolar amount of the sodium salt of acetylacetone and ethylacetoacetate in ethanolic solution at room temperature readily gives pyrazole derivatives⁹ (14) and (15), respectively, in fair to good yields (Scheme 1).

The alkylhydrazonyl halides resemble their aryl counterparts in respect of their ability to undergo displacement reactions with nucleophilic substrates¹⁰. Thus, the chlorine atom of (1) is found to undergo displacement reaction with a series of nucleophilic reagents, viz., sodium azide, hydrazine hydrate, ammonia and phenyl hydrazine to afford

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Scheme-1

X		Y		X		Y	
4.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}=\text{CH}$	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{CH}$		7.	O	14.	R = CH ₃
5.	$4\text{-BrC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}=\text{CH}$	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{CH}$		8.	O	15.	R = OC ₂ H ₅
	O			9.	O	16.	R = N ₃
6.	O	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{CH}$		10.	O	17.	R = NHNH ₂
				11.	O	18.	R = NH ₂
				12.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{N}$	19.	R = C ₆ H _{5}-\text{N}=\text{N}-}
				13.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{N}$		

hydrazonil azide (16), hydrazidines (17) and (18) and formajan (19), respectively (Scheme 1).

All the compounds synthesized in this study are listed in Table 1. All the products give correct elemental analysis and their structures are supported by ir and nmr spectroscopy (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points were measured with a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Products were purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina or silica gel and purity is checked by tlc. The nmr spectra are recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and chemical shifts are expressed in δ values. IR spectra are recorded on a Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer and uv spectra on Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

N-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-acetohydrazonyl chloride (1): 2,4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone of acetaldehyde was prepared as described in the literature⁵.

A stream of dry chlorine gas was cautiously passed into a well cooled solution of thrice crystallised hydrazone (5 g) in 30 ml chloroform till the hydrazone goes into a clear red coloured solution. The solution finally lightens in colour and *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-acetohydrazonyl chloride (1) separates out as a bright yellow crystalline mass.

The mother liquor after slight concentration and further treatment with methanol afforded another crop of hydrazonyl chloride, m.p. 149°, yield 90%. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃): δ 2.57 (s, 3H, CH₃); 11.5 (s, 1, NH); 7.90, 8.07, 8.40, 8.50, 9.25 (2s+3d, 3-ArH). IR (KBr): 1630 (C=N), 1500 and 1340 (NO₂), 3100 (NH), 640 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). UV λ_{max} 364 nm. (Found: C, 37.32; H, 2.62; N, 21.75. Calcd. for C₈H₇N₄O₄Cl; C, 37.20; H, 2.71; N, 21.70%).

Preparation of cycloadducts (4-13):

General method: To a solution of hydrazonyl chloride (1) in 50 ml of dry organic solvents was added dipolarophiles in equimolar amount and the mixture stirred under ice-cold condition. Triethylamine in equimolar amount was then added dropwise under nitrogen. The solution was refluxed and stirred for 2-4 hr and then left overnight. The resulting precipitate was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure. Compounds were chromatographed and recrystallized from appropriate solvents (Table 1).

Preparation of pyrazoles (14, 15): To an ethanolic solution of sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium metal (0.11 g; 0.005 g atom) and alcohol (20 ml), was added 0.005 mole of the active methylene compound. After stirring for 0.5 hr at room temp., the hydrazonyl chloride (1) was added and stirring continued for 4-6 hr. Conventional workup⁶ of the reaction mixture afforded the products in excellent yield.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE PRODUCTS (3—19)

Compd. No.	m. p. °C	Recystn. solvent	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Molecular formula	¹ H-NMR (CDCl ₃ /TMS) δ (ppm)
			C	H	N		
3.	189-90	MeOH	43.31 (43.24)	2.52 (2.70)	25.42 (25.23)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆	2.42 (s, 6H, CH ₃); 7.86–9.35 (m, 6H, Ar-H)
4.	179-81	MeOH	64.23 (64.18)	4.23 (4.18)	2.87 (3.02)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆	1.90 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 4.44 (d, 1H, CH); 5.67 (d, 1H, CH); 7.80–9.2 (m, 13H, ArH)
5.	194-98	EtOH	54.32 (54.14)	3.15 (3.33)	10.97 (11.00)	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆ Br	2.00 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 4.50 (d, 1H, CH); 5.80 (d, 1H, CH); 7.9–9.6 (m, 12H, ArH)
6.	240-41	MeOH	54.92 (54.87)	3.50 (3.62)	16.89 (16.94)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆	1.85 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 7.28–8.57 (m, 8H, Ar-H); 10.9 (s, 1H, CH)
7.	224-25	CHCl ₃	53.79 (53.63)	3.82 (3.91)	15.72 (15.61)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₆ H ₄	1.56 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 3.89 (s, 3H, OCH ₃); 7.26–8.50 (m, 7H, ArH); 10.84 (s, 1H, CH)
8.	204	C ₆ H ₆ -PE	52.46 (52.32)	3.52 (3.48)	16.42 (16.28)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆	1.56* (s, 1H, OH); 2.13 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 7.18–9.98 (m, 7H, ArH); 11.46 (s, 1H, CH)
9.	140-43	CHCl ₃ -EtOH	52.41 (52.32)	3.59 (3.48)	16.48 (16.28)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆	2.10* (s, 1H, OH); 2.15 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 7.49–10.27 (m, 7H, ArH); 11.70 (s, 1H, CH)
10.	172-73	C ₆ H ₆	51.19 (51.33)	3.24 (3.14)	14.90 (14.87)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₇	1.65* (s, 1H, OH); 2.01 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 3.93 (s, 3H, OCH ₃); 7.25–9.94 (m, 6H, Ar-H); 11.48 (s, 1H, CH)
11.	152	EtOH	52.62 (52.57)	4.03 (4.12)	14.81 (14.69)	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₇	1.89* (s, 1H, OH); 1.39 (t, 3H, CH ₃); 2.06 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 4.22 (q, 2H, CH ₂); 7.29–9.93 (m, 6H, ArH); 11.48 (s, 1H, CH)
12.	228-29	CHCl ₃ -MeOH	62.43 (62.53)	4.32 (4.21)	17.09 (17.36)	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆	2.02 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 7.92–9.86 (m, 14H, Ar-H+CH)
13.	262	DMF-MeOH	60.20 (60.14)	4.20 (4.05)	16.59 (16.70)	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₆	2.11 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 7.8–9.82 (m, 13H, Ar-H+CH)
14.	166-67	EtOAc	51.42 (51.31)	3.81 (3.94)	18.12 (18.42)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆	2.53 (d, 9H, CH ₃); 7.24–8.84 (m, 3H, Ar-H)
15.	151-53	EtOH	50.32 (50.29)	4.18 (4.19)	16.80 (16.76)	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₆	1.43 (t, 3H, CH ₃); 2.46 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 2.51 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 4.34 (q, 2H, CH ₂); 7.26–8.33 (m, 3H, Ar-H)
16.	125-26	Acetone-H ₂ O	36.01 (36.22)	2.46 (2.64)	36.73 (36.98)	C ₆ H ₇ N ₂ O ₆	
17.	215-16	EtOH	37.49 (37.79)	3.57 (3.93)	33.18 (33.07)	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₆	
18.	139-41	CHCl ₃ -EtOH	40.23 (40.17)	3.59 (3.76)	29.11 (29.28)	C ₆ H ₉ N ₂ O ₆	2.06 (t, 3H, CH ₃); 7.18–8.96 (m, 5H, ArH+NH ₂)
19.	199	EtOH	51.01 (51.21)	3.79 (3.65)	25.49 (25.60)	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆	2.37 (s, 3H, CH ₃); 7.27–9.17 (m, 8H, ArH)

s=singlet, d=doublet, t=triplet, q=quartet.

* NMR spectra in D₂O + CDCl₃ show no peak for OH group.

IR spectra of the compounds show all the characteristic peaks for C=N, NO₂, C=C, OH and C=O groups in their specific range; yield of the products ranged from 40–80%.

Preparation of N-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-C-methyl-hydrazonyl azide (16): Hydrazonyl chloride (1) (0.4 g) was added to 70% dioxane-water and slightly warmed to dissolve it. When a clear solution was obtained, a solution of sodium azide (0.14 g) in 20.0 ml of the same solvent was added into the reaction mixture. On cooling, hydrazonyl azide (16) started separating out as a yellow needle shape product.

Preparation of hydrazidines (17, 18) and formazan (19): Hydrazonyl chloride (1; 0.6 g) was stirred in 40.0 ml of 95% ethanol at room temperature and hydrazine hydrate, ammonia or phenyl hydrazine (0.6 ml) was added dropwise. The solution became deep red, and brown red solid precipitated. This was collected after allowing to stand for 4 hr and recrystallised thrice with ethanol to obtain the pure sample of hydrazidines (17, 18) and formazan (19), respectively.

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